

Symbolic Violence Among The Students Of The Primary School

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 21, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: October 19, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Symbolic Violence, Direct Violence, Indirect Violence</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4540780</p>	<p><i>The role of social media has increased dramatically in different context such as business, politics, and healthcare promotion. Though, the factors enhancing the adoption of social media as a tool of health promotion in Malaysia have not been embraced practically. This article aims to identify conceptual framework for social media adoption by Malaysian healthcare practitioners (MHPs) as a health platform promoter in Malaysia. It helps to deliver an effective message on the available social media at the lowest costs and timely manner, to improve government performance in facing healthcare challenges. The study framework is based on the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) proposing that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions have a significant positive effect on the adoption of social media platforms. This study provides an important consideration of the current global healthcare orientation and the trends innovation that should be adopted by the government or any MHPs which might help of optimizing the use of limited resources. The expected result would also highlight the effective factors on health practitioners to adopt social media as a communication tool that can be used to enhance people awareness about diseases prevention and staying healthy.</i></p>

Introduction

Violence throughout humanity has taken many forms, direct and indirect, hidden and overt, and from physical violence in the simplest and most instinctive form through the use of muscle force in defense or even to satisfy the human instinct for victory, to symbolic violence that takes many paths, methods and manifestations, the danger of which is no less than Physical violence, but can take broader and deeper dimensions and include all forms of intangible violence that harm the other, whether through speech, language, or various forms of expression. (Laouira Omar, 2003: p.11).

Violence against children in schools has a set of psychological and social effects, such as aggression, withdrawal, and antisocial behavior, such as students' disrespect for their teachers, and then their dislike for school, until the student practices a cycle of violence on himself and others and symbolic violence among them, and the consequences thereof. Negativity on society (Saliba, 1967: 109).

The phenomenon of violence, including the symbolic one, is a problem facing school students at all levels and stages, especially elementary ones, in which the manifestations of violence appear in its various forms and have a great impact on the formation of his personality, so this stage needs special treatment and care and great attention to be able to deliver students to a healthy physical, mental and emotional building. Therefore, he is most in need of those who listen to their problems, understand them, and help them overcome problems. The problem of the current research can be identified by answering the following question (Do primary school students have symbolic violence....?)

Research's Importance

Violence has become a general and daily phenomenon experienced by all members of society, as it finds acceptance in some circles of our societies due to the conditions of wars and economic, political and social crises (Al-Qaisi, 2004: 2). Bourdieu shed light on this dangerous type of violence, and this concept is one of Bourdieu's most brilliant discoveries and its importance and is almost in his name as he sees it as violence that involves types of submission that are not perceived as they are, but which seem legitimized and that they are Muslim. Violence is invisible, but impactful and dangerous (Chevalier et al., 2013: 223).

Bandura pointed out that aggressive behavior, including symbolic violence, is an educated social behavior that an individual learns through modeling. The process of acquiring roles that takes place through the process of reincarnation according to (Freud's) viewpoint, who considered reincarnation the basic logic in the theory of socialization, and that the process of acquiring roles takes place through this stage, such as introducing the justifications for violence against his students as a necessary mechanism according to Johnson's belief to play the role The teacher, this means that the concept of education is identical with the concept of upbringing,

and the concept of modeling is inseparable from the concept of reincarnation, especially since social, economic, political and cultural conditions are among the factors affecting the process of socialization (Sabila, 1987: 43).

Research's Aims

The current research aims to identify symbolic violence among primary school students.

Search Limits:

The current research is determined by identifying symbolic violence among primary school students in Baghdad governorate in the six education directorates (Al-Karkh 1, 2, and 3) (Rusafa 1, 2, and 3) for the academic year (2019-2020).

Defining Terms:

Symbolic violence

Define it by Bourdieu (2009): It is a kind of hidden and hidden violence that reaches types of submission that are not perceived as they are, but which seem legitimized. (Purdue, 2009: 8-9).

Theoretical Definition: Since the two researchers have adopted Bourdieu's point of view to define the concept of symbolic violence, the theoretical definition adopted by the researchers is the same definition of the referred to Bourdieu.

Procedural Definition

The total score obtained by the respondent by answering the paragraphs of the symbolic violence scale prepared in the current research.

Theoretical Framework

1.The theory explaining symbolic violence: Purdue's theory:

Pierre Bourdieu (1930-2002), the French researcher, is considered one of the founders and promoters of the idea of symbolic violence. He believes that violence takes two main forms, the first being physical violence and a different demonstration, and the second is symbolic violence that between some of its methods and its effectiveness in stabilizing the foundations of societal authoritarianism. Hence, it seems impossible to talk about human societies free from violence.

Bourdieu notes that it is possible to destroy a person without those around him noticing this matter, through apparently innocent words, signals, assumptions, or just exclusion, this (hidden) violence but recurring, chronic and sometimes daily, which afflicts the psyche of the person who suffers from it often in silence and thus leads him.

To retreat to one-self, fighting the best of his energies and creativity, which then withdraws to his way of dealing with his small or large surroundings, and to not taking into account his reactions, which are often characterized by the features of recklessness and recklessness, thus leading to extremism and violence. His concept of symbolic violence does not take into account the subjective experience of an individual's suffering.

However, there are many social phenomena of great importance, linked in another way with symbolic violence and facilitating its observation, that is, that results from harm to self-esteem or collective representations of the self, and is a source of identity decline, for example hostile and racist speeches.

Every authority has symbolic violence, that is, every authority that tries to impose its values and connotations that it is legitimate, and that any influence based on symbolic violence or any influence succeeds in imposing certain connotations and imposing them as legitimate connotations (Pierbordio, 1994: 5).

Bourdieu's concept of symbolic violence constitutes a mental starting point for revealing its mental and ideological activities that society exercises in class to form individual minds, through moral authority. This means that symbolic violence establishes a form of hidden moral authority that imposes a system of ideas, connotations, meanings and relationships as sustainable and Cases this authority works to hide power relations in the authority or through symbolic violence itself, and it can appear at all ages.(Watafa, 2012: 24).

As symbolic violence is related to many concepts and premises of the economic and social class difference that appears among some who disagree with others in these principles, and Bourdieu asserts that symbolic violence is one of the forms of non-physical violence, and influences economic, social, political and religious life and in all forms of human behavior. And this kind of gentle and polite violence makes its victims accept it and submit to its coercions without resistance, because in the context of life a person accepts a number of values and beliefs as axioms and universals that impose themselves easily and automatically from language and speech, and all other forms of communication. (Purdue, 2008: 2-3).

Purdy asserts that symbolic violence is not based on any moral or intellectual criteria because it aims to insult the dignity of the individual, deny him his human rights, and ignore his psychological and social needs. (Watafa, 2009: 71).

2-Previous studies

A- Abdul Majeed's study (2013):

Title: (Causes of symbolic violence among elementary school students and ways to address them).

Objective: To identify the causes of symbolic violence among students and to deal with them.

The sample: The sample consisted of female guides and mentors for grades five and six working in elementary schools in the General Directorates of Education in Baghdad governorate, whose number is (860) counselors (Karkh and Rusafa).

Results

After analyzing the results, the researcher concluded:

The reasons related to the field of social environment are ranked first among other causes of symbolic violence among primary school students, then the school environment and economic, and reasons related to the field of public health and psychological reasons. And while all of these causes and causes stand behind this phenomenon. The study proposals included conducting similar studies on the same subject of study in other places and focusing on the importance of introducing this type of violence.

B-Nasir's study (2015):

Title: (Symbolic violence among elementary school students from the point of view of classroom counselors and ways to address it).

Objective: It aims to recognize the reality of the use of symbolic violence by students and to know the effect that this behavior has on (student frustration, academic decline, destruction of educational property).

The sample: The sample included classroom counselors for primary schools, especially the fifth and sixth primary grades, with a percentage (10%) of the study population.

Society: The study population included (8626) male and female students in the schools of the General Directorates in Baghdad Governorate (Karkh – Rusafa).

Tool: The researcher used the symbolic violence scale

Results

The results indicated: The reasons related to the field of social environment are ranked first among other causes of symbolic violence among elementary school students and the loss of one or both parents was in addition to the wrong practices for them by providing alternatives in the event of destroying property and without directing the child In addition to the lack of training of children in emotional control in directing their behavior in the event of anger, as well as the acute mood of the mother or father, or both, with a decrease in the social level of some parents and watching films of symbolic violence. (Abdul Hussein, 2015: 107).

Procedures of the research

This chapter includes a description of the methodology and the selection of the appropriate experimental design that the researchers followed, as well as a description of the research community, its sample, the research tool for measuring symbolic violence and conducting its psychometric properties, and the statistical methods used in processing the statistical data.

Approach of Research

The two researchers used the descriptive approach to achieve the goal of the research because it is an appropriate and appropriate approach to the research procedures and reach the results (Al-Manizel and Al-Atoum, 2010: 198).

Research Community:

The current research community consists of primary school pupils for the academic year (2019-2020) and the number is (400) students for morning study in (8) schools in Baghdad / Al-Karkh governorate (first, second, and third) Al-Rusafa (first, second, third) for the academic year. So, (2019-2020) and Table (1) will illustrate this:

Table 1)(

It shows the names of the schools and the numbers of students in the research community

Seq.	The name of the school			The number of students of fifth grade	Total
1	Baghdad	First Karkh	Mixed Al-Baghdadiya Elementary	80	459
2	Baghdad	First Karkh	Mixed El-Akkad Elementary	63	
3	Baghdad	Second Karkh	Mixed Al-Khansaa Elementary	57	
4	Baghdad	Third Karkh	Mixed Dar Al-Hikma Primary	103	

5	Baghdad	First Rusafa	Mixed Aisha Elementary	38	
6	Baghdad	Second Rusafa	Karbala Elementary for Boys	49	
7	Baghdad	Third Rusafa	the martyr Sheikh Hussein Al-Maliki Elementary School for Boys	69	

Statistical analysis sample:

For the purpose of conducting the statistical analysis of the symbolic violence scale, the researchers selected a sample consisting of (400) students from the elementary stage (see Anastasia, 1988)) The sample size of the statistical analysis of the paragraphs is appropriate if (400-500) individuals from the research community, so the researchers chose The sample is randomly distributed equally among the schools of the six districts in Baghdad governorate (Al-Karkh - Al-Rusafa) of primary school students from the fifth grade of primary school, with (50) pupils for each of the schools, as in the following table:

(Table 2)

Distribution of the statistical analysis sample by schools

School name	location	number of students
Mixed Al-Baghdadiya Elementary	First Karkh	50
Mixed El-Akkad Elementary	First Karkh	50
Mixed Al-Anwar Elementary	First Karkh	50
Mixed Al-Khansaa Elementary	Second Karkh	50
Mixed Dar Al-Hikma Primary	Third Karkh	50
Mixed Aisha Elementary	First Rusafa	50
Karbala Elementary for Boys	Second Rusafa	50
The martyr Sheikh Hussein Al-Maliki Elementary School for Boys	Third Rusafa	50
Total		400

Research Tool: Symbolic Violence Scale:

The two researchers followed a number of steps in constructing the symbolic violence scale as well as extracting the validity and consistency of the scale, which are as follows:

Scale planning:

After the researchers reviewed the literature, sources, and previous studies related to the research variable, which are represented by the Majeed scale (2013), the Nasser scale (2015), the Khazraji scale (2017), and the Shako scale (2016), it was found that the scales that were viewed were for samples different from The current research sample, so the two researchers built the symbolic violence scale according to the current research sample, following the following steps:

Defining the concept to be measured:

In light of what the researchers obtained from previous literature referred to above on the symbolic violence scale, the two researchers adopted a definition (Bourdieu, 2009) to define the concept of the subject to be studied and defined it as "a type of violence that shows gentle behaviors that make its victims accept it and submit to its coercions without resistance. It is a hidden and dormant violence that reaches types of submission that are not perceived as they are, but which seem legitimized (Bourdieu, 2009: 8-9).

Preparation of scale instructions:

The two researchers prepared the scale instructions where they did not indicate the name of the scale or the goal, but rather indicated how to answer the scale paragraphs, reassure the respondents of the confidentiality of this answer and urge them to answer honestly, objectively and frankly and to answer all the paragraphs and not leave any paragraph without an answer with an example of how to answer.

-Clarity of instructions and understanding of paragraphs and method of correction:

To ensure the clarity of the scale's instructions, is understand its expressions and vocabulary and how to answer it by the sample members, the two researchers applied the scale to an exploratory sample of (100) students. The instructions and scale phrases were proven clear and clear in terms of meaning and wording, and the time taken to answer the scale was calculated if it was (15) Minutes (Spring 2009: 96).

Correct the scale:

The researchers prepared the symbolic violence scale, and with each paragraph two alternatives graded the answer, which is (yes, no), and when corrected, the scores are given (1, 0) for the alternatives to the answer.

Perform paragraph analysis.

It is considered one of the important steps in construction procedures and its goal is to determine the validity of the paragraphs and the psychometric properties that are available in them. This process is divided into two processes:

a.Logical Analysis (virtual honesty):

Bell mentioned that the best way to verify the validity of the paragraphs is for a number of distinguished experts to determine their validity to measure the characteristic for which they were set (Ebel, 1972: p.556), and thus the researchers identified the 15 paragraphs of the scale in Appendix (2) distributed On (two alternatives) and presented to the experts and specialists in psychological counseling, psychology and psychometrics, Appendix (1) clarifies this, in order to express their opinions on its validity, as all the paragraphs and corresponding topics were approved.

B. statistical analysis

The statistical analysis of the paragraphs is a major and important step in building the psychological and educational measures because it indicates the extent to which the content of the paragraph represents the situation it was prepared to measure, and that the aim of the analysis of the paragraphs of the scale is to maintain the good paragraphs that distinguish between the individuals subject to the measurement, as one of the important conditions for the paragraphs of the psychological measures is It is characterized by strong discriminatory power between individuals with high scores and individuals with low scores in the condition to be measured (Gronlund, 1981: p.254).

Statistical analysis of the Symbolic Violence Scale

1.Discriminatory Power:

The concept of discriminatory power depends on the existence of two extremes, and since the sample of statistical analysis is (400) students, the two researchers adopted a percentage (27%) to determine the members of the upper and lower groups, and this percentage equals (108) students for the upper group and (108) students for the lower group.

Members of the upper and lower groups are (216) students. And since the answer to the scale paragraphs (yes, no) and the correction of the scale paragraphs is binary (1, zero), the researchers adopted the coefficient (phi correlation). To reveal the discriminatory power of the paragraphs, so the paragraph is considered true if the strength of the relationship is positively significant, and to reveal the significance of the relationship, the two researchers used (chi square), and when comparing the calculated value of the (chi square) test with the tabular value at the degree of freedom (1) and at the level of significance (0,5- 0) and it is (84,3). We find that all the paragraphs are sincere and did not exclude any paragraph from the paragraphs.

2- The relation of the paragraph to the total degree:

The two researchers verified this indicator by finding the relationship between the score of each paragraph and the total score of the scale using the Point Piserial correlation coefficient and the correlation coefficients is ranged between (0,202 - 0,412) and all the paragraphs were significant when compared to the critical value of the correlation coefficient of (0.098) and the level of significance is (0.05) and with a degree of freedom (398). Thus, Table (3) illustrates this.

Table (3)

Correlation coefficients between paragraph score and overall score for the symbolic violence scale

Paragraph number	Paragraph correlation coefficient of total score	Paragraph number	Paragraph correlation coefficient of total score	Paragraph number	Paragraph correlation coefficient of total score
1	0,298	6	0,281	11	0,358
2	0,303	7	0,202	12	0,286
3	0,412	8	0,333	13	0,329
4	0,280	9	0,295	14	0,254
5	0,272	10	0,340	15	0,275

Stability of scale:

The stability was extracted by two methods and the stability sample was for the retest method (50). As for the stability sample for the Alpha Cronbach method, the two researchers used (100) individuals from the adult statistical analysis sample, who were randomly selected.

the method of extracting the

The value of the stability factor

stability	
retest method	0,81
Alpha Cronbach's method	0,78

- Statistical indicators for the symbolic violence scale

The most prominent statistical indicators of the symbolic violence scale

statistical indicators		value
N	Valid	400
Mean		8,755
Median		9
Mode		11
Std. Deviation		2,060
Variance		4,246
Skewness		0,252-
Kurtosis		0,382-
Range		10
Minimum		3
Maximum		13

Presentation, interpretation and discussion of results

View and interpret results:

-Identify symbolic violence among primary school students

To identify symbolic violence among students, the two researchers applied the symbolic violence test consisting of (15) items on (100) students. The arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the scores of the sample

members were calculated in the symbolic violence test, in order to compare them with the theoretical average of the test, and the T-test for one sample was used to identify The significance of the difference between the arithmetic mean and the theoretical average, as it was found that the members of the sample have symbolic violence because the difference is real, not caused by chance and in favor of the arithmetic mean of the sample, and the results are as shown in Table (5).

Table (5)

T-test results to identify the level of symbolic violence among students

The sample	arithmetic mean	standard deviation	theoretical mean	T-test results	
				tabular	Computed
100	10,17	1,68	7,5	1,98	15,70

* Tabular T value = (1.98), at the level of significance (0.05), and with the degree of freedom (99).

Since the calculated T value is greater than the tabular T value, this means that the individuals of the research sample have symbolic violence and this result can be interpreted according to Purdy theory and that this type of violence appears in different age groups and generates a state of practice for those violent behaviors towards objects and individuals, and that the environment surrounding the students has it.

A clear influence on learning negative thoughts and behaviors alike, and Bourdieu also believes that it is impossible to talk about human societies free of violence, and the school community applies this idea to him, and this result was consistent with the study of Nasser (2015).

Recommendations:

In light of the results of the current research, the researchers recommended the following:

- 1.Using the symbolic violence measurement tool prepared by the two researchers to detect those who have symbolic violence from elementary school students by educational counselors.
- 2.There must be explicit laws that prohibit the use of corporal punishment on students.
- 3.Establishing new laws against teachers that contribute to reducing their resort to verbal violence because they are a role model and model for some students, and it must be at the cultural level that they are on.
- 4.The Ministry of Education should write books on human rights and the principles of democracy, provided that it is a curriculum that starts from the primary stage, because democracy and human rights are behavior and culture that a person is brought up on since childhood.

The proposals:

To complement the current research, the researchers suggest conducting the following studies and research:

- 1.Foremost studies dealing with the impact of social and family upbringing in promoting symbolic violence.
- 2.Study the effect of cognitive-behavioral counseling on reducing symbolic violence among samples of elementary and intermediate school students
- 3.Conducting a similar study for our topic, to include the preparatory environment in the same current study areas.

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